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HISTORICAL ASPECTS OF LAND PLOTS VALUATION IN RUSSIA

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Abstract

The article considers the historical aspects of land valuation based on the cadastral value of land plots, in connection with which there is a need to obtain an objective value of this value, calculated taking into account all the factors affecting it. This task is especially urgent for such actively involved in economic turnover of lands as lands of urban settlements.

Keywords: land, farm, history, country, valuation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The state cadastral valuation of residential lands in general and lands intended for residential buildings in particular is carried out on the basis of an extensive list of regulatory and legal literature, in which the most important document regulating the process of mass appraisal works (after the Technical Recommendations were canceled) remains the Methodological Guidelines for the state cadastral valuation of residential lands.

Currently, the methodology of land resources assessment is a dynamically developing system. With the development of the legitimate base and software, new approaches to the determination of previously unaccounted for indicators, such as encumbrances, are spreading. The current state of cadastral services of cities allows to form databases on zones with a special regime of use. Despite numerous studies on this problem and the presence in the normative-legal literature of indications on the need to take into account encumbrances in the process of cadastral valuation of land plots, at present such accounting is not performed.

II. METHODOLOGY AND RESULTS

The methodological basis of the article on land valuation is the fundamental works of domestic and foreign scientists in the field of finance, valuation activities, statistics, among which we can mention: A.A. Varlamova, N.V. Volovicha, A.P. Vorontsova, C.B. Gribovskogo, V.A. Goremykina, A.G. Gryaznova, V.A. Dzhukha, V.A. Litovchenko, N.G. Kuznetsova and other scientists and practitioners.

But the issues of obtaining adequate results of appraisal works related to the determination of the cadastral value of real estate objects, which would allow to avoid litigation both on the conduct of appraisal procedures and on the reliability of the value of the object remain insufficiently developed.

Not everyone knows, but the first mention of real estate valuation appeared in 1861 when the fiscal cadastre was created after the abolition of serfdom. Further, in 1864, the "Regulation on Zemstvo Institutions" was published, which changed the taxation of citizens depending on the profitability of property, so the profitability of land was determined by the average yield and income from renting land. Urban real estate, or rather the real estate tax, was assessed according to the "Urban Status" of 1870, as well as in terms of income and value (costs of creation or acquisition). In 1893, the Law on the Valuation of Immovable Property subject to zemstvo fees was published. After the release of this law, various instructions and methods for evaluating real estate, as well as the creation of evaluation commissions, begin to be developed and published.

It can be stated that the valuation of real estate and other property in the Soviet period was in a state of stagnation. The accumulated pre-revolutionary experience was irretrievably lost, and the need for real estate valuation itself practically disappeared. However, with the increasing need to determine the value of real estate, departmental instructions were used, which were based, as a rule, on the use of the estimated cost of construction. Unfortunately, this period did not bring any significant benefit in the history of the development of real estate valuation.

With the collapse of the Soviet Union, the emergence of private property and the development of market relations in the early 90s, there is a need for an independent valuation of property and, first of all, the valuation of real estate. This is how a new professional direction begins to be created – property valuation.

In 1993, the Society of Appraisers was established, which by 1995 already had 48 regional branches. Further, the real estate valuation goes through several significant stages. These are the introduction of a new profession of appraiser, the adoption of the Law on Valuation Activities, the adoption of valuation standards, licensing of valuation activities, increased requirements for the education of appraisers, insurance of valuation activities, self-regulation of valuation activities. The state also does not stand aside and actively attracts appraisers through the accreditation mechanism to solve important tasks. Registers of real estate located both in Russia and abroad and its market value assessment are being created. Evaluation is increasingly penetrating into everyday life. There is an assessment for the purposes of legal proceedings, insurance, damage assessment, collateral lending, mergers and division of property, incorporation into the authorized capital, inheritance, redemption of state property, revaluation of fixed assets, etc.

The search for ways to solve such a problem is of great importance in the practice of application of cadastral valuation results by users, including investors during privatization of enterprises, property taxpayers, notaries when conducting real estate transactions, executive authorities when granting real estate for lease, including to small and medium-sized businesses, and others. This is also important for municipalities in general as a factor of financial sustainability of the territory.

The sources of information and statistical base were the data of the federal statistics service, reporting data of state and municipal authorities (medium and large cities), analytical reviews of the results of cadastral valuation contained in scientific publications and periodicals

To achieve the set goal, the methods of comparative analysis, the method of statistical groupings, the method of scientific abstraction were used, which allowed to ensure the validity of the results of land valuations.

For many years, the State has used the concept of the inventory value of land for tax purposes. It was far from the market price, so the amount of land tax turned out to be extremely insignificant. The situation changed dramatically when the concept of "cadastral value of land" entered into legal practice, which significantly approached the market price. And now the amount of payments linked to the results of the cadastral valuation of land can be impressive. Let's take a closer look at what are the features of cadastral valuation for different types of land, how it is carried out, and most importantly, why it is important that the information in the Unified Register corresponds to the real value of the site.

What is a cadastral valuation and why is it needed? The State Land Cadastre (register) is a systematized and ordered list of all land plots on the territory of Russia. In other words, it is a database of all territories. Each site has its own description and accompanying documents.

Total accounting makes it possible to assess land use, identify trends and avoid violations. In addition, each land plot is also a real estate object that can be sold or bought. In this situation, the question arises of determining the cost. In order to avoid disagreements, a cadastral valuation of land is carried out.

Cadastral value is one of the main characteristics of the site. Cadastral valuation of land plots allows this value to be identified and officially recorded. This is necessary to solve a whole range of tasks:

At the state level, to create a unified system of taxation of lands that are in state or private ownership, which allows you to calculate taxes as accurately as possible, fill budgets, and make forecasts regarding tax collections.

At the level of the subjects of the Russian Federation - for making decisions on the rational use of land, privatization, distribution and redistribution, issuance of building permits — in short, for effective land management.

At the level of private owners - for the fair calculation of taxes, for determining the market value, for the purchase and sale, lease, investment in land, etc.

The land plots that have passed the cadastral assessment are entered into a Unified register indicating not only the identified value, but also the owner. An extract from the register is a direct confirmation of the legality of land use. The specified amount is used to calculate the property tax. Cadastral valuation of land and real estate is carried out before any transactions: sale, donation, lease. This indicator is necessary for calculating the rent for the use of public lands. Based on it, government subsidies are calculated. The cadastral value becomes the starting price when putting up land for auction.

Like most such activities, the assessment of a particular plot of land is carried out in several stages. First of all, the expert familiarizes himself with the existing situation, determines the types of assessment activities that need to be carried out. At the same step, based on the complexity and urgency of the upcoming evaluation, the cost of the procedure is established. After the preliminary activities, an agreement is signed between the initiator of the expertise and the expert center, which clearly states the goals and objectives of the study, as well as the questions that the specialist will have to answer at the end of the work.

At the next stage, land plots are assessed directly. The expert examines the documentation submitted by the customer, conducts an assessment according to the methods chosen by him, compares the results and calculates the final value of the land plot - market, rental mortgage or investment, depending on the task set before him.

At the last stage, the land valuation specialist forms an expert opinion - the main result of the expert's activity and a document on the basis of which the initiator of the valuation can take further steps or present it in court to confirm its position. The expert opinion necessarily includes a description of all evaluation activities, their results, and the final opinion of the expert. In addition, the conclusion is accompanied by copies of all documents studied, as well as documents of the appraisal company, copies of diplomas of specialists and so on.

The expert opinion can be handed over to the initiator of the expert examination in person at the office of the expert center, as well as delivered by mail or through a courier service.

The value of the land plot specified in the conclusion is valid for six months from the date of its receipt. The only exception is the assessment of land plots transferred into ownership when a new owner enters into inheritance rights. In relation to land and land plots, land can be assessed not only as a right of ownership, but also other rights - for example, the right to lease. The market value of the right to lease a land plot depends on the powers of the lessee granted to him under the lease agreement, the term of the lease agreement, the presence of encumbrances and the permitted use of the land plot. The cost of the lease right also depends on the expected value and probability of obtaining income from the use of the rental object for a certain period of time with the most effective use of it.

An independent valuation of land or an assessment of land resources in Moscow, Rostov-on-Don, Voronezh, Krasnodar, Maykop, Stavropol, Barnaul and other cities can be carried out for the following purposes:

- getting a loan from a bank;
- contribution to the authorized capital;
- sale of a land plot;
- joining the inheritance;
- drawing up a business plan;
- division of property;
- purchase of a land plot from municipal ownership.

Documents are required to assess the value of a land plot:

Supporting document: Extract from the Unified State Register of Legal Entities or Certificate of state registration of the right; Cadastral plan of the land plot (if available); Information about the availability and condition of engineering communications; If available, information about real estate objects located on land plots.

In order to assess the land, information is used to ensure the reliability of the land assessment report as a document containing evidence-based information. Land valuation is always carried out as of a specific date.

The timing and cost of the assessment depends on the type and location of the land being assessed, as well as the objectives of the assessment.

Today, land plots remain the leading area for profitable investments. The allocated territory is bought, sold, and leased for long-term and short-term rentals.

The price is formed under the influence of several important factors, for example, the location of the object, market demand and supply.

The examination of a private or public land object and the official clarification of its value includes the analysis of the following data: availability of communications, their quality, the ability to connect to centralized engineering networks; the results of the survey of an engineering-geological and engineering-geodetic nature, including the composition of the soil, terrain features;

Before making any transactions, it is necessary to check their economic validity. This allows you to identify in time whether it is worth giving the requested amount to the owner, or it would be more profitable to continue the search.

III. CONCLUSION

Accordingly, a correct and professional assessment provides an opportunity to maximize the efficient and rational use of available land resources. It is also necessary for accurate data recording. Due to the multifaceted nature of the concept of land, it is necessary to clearly define the purpose of use of each specific land plot. Further it will be possible to determine the choice of optimal methods of assessment. Accordingly, the objectives of the appraisal fully affect the result of its implementation. As stated in paragraph 3 of FSO №. 2, the purpose of evaluation work is to find out the value of a certain object. The type of appraisal is determined in the task for it, taking into account the intended application of the result obtained. Paragraph 5 of FSO №. 2 indicates what types of value of the object to be appraised can be, among them: investment, market, cadastral, liquidation value.

All of the above assumes that land valuation can be individual and mass. Individual provides for the consideration of single objects to meet the needs of individual owners of land plots. The mass one is used for various state purposes: taxation and others.

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ИСТОРИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ОЦЕНКИ ЗЕМЕЛЬНЫХ УЧАСТКОВ В РОССИИ

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Аннотация

В статье рассматриваются исторические аспекты оценки земли на основе кадастровой стоимости земельных участков, в связи с чем возникает необходимость получения объективного значения этой стоимости, рассчитанного с учетом всех влияющих на нее факторов. Эта задача особенно актуальна для таких активно вовлеченных в хозяйственный оборот земель, как земли городских поселений.

Ключевые слова: земля, ферма, история, страна, оценка.

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